

Synthesis and Analytical Applications of Thorium(IV) Phosphosilicate—A New Mercury Selective Cation Exchanger : Effect of Gamma Irradiation on its Ion-Exchange Behaviour

K. G. VARSHNEY, UMA SHARMA and SIMA RANI

Analytical Laboratories, Chemistry Section,

Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

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A new mercury selective inorganic cation exchanger, thorium(IV) phosphosilicate has been synthesized and studied for its ion-exchange behaviour. The exchanger has been characterized by chemical analysis and infrared spectra, X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetry and pH-titration. The effect of gamma irradiation on its ion-exchange behaviour has also been studied. Finally, the utility of the material has been demonstrated by achieving some binary separations of metal ions, and by separating Hg(II) from some synthetic amalgam solutions.

THORIUM phosphate prepared by Alberti and Costantino¹ showed an excellent ion exchange behaviour and was found suitable for preparing support-free inorganic sheets^{2,3}. As silicates are generally temperature resistant and stable under chemical attack⁴, it is interesting to study a material which consists of both phosphate and silicate groups attached to a metal. Titanium(IV) phosphosilicate⁵, for example, has been found useful for the separation of Zr(IV) from Nb(V) and of Pu(IV) from Cs(I). Similarly, phosphosilicates of Zr(IV), Ce(IV) and Sn(IV) have been synthesized⁶⁻⁹ and their ion-exchange properties studied. The present paper reports a systematic study on the synthesis and properties of a new mercury selective thorium(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS) cation exchanger. The exchanger has also been utilized for the column separation of metal ions from some binary mixtures and of mercury(II) from some synthetic amalgam solutions.

Experimental

Thorium nitrate, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and all the acids (phosphoric, nitric, sulphuric, hydrochloric, perchloric and organic) used in this study were obtained from B.D.H., Poole, England. Sodium silicate, $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, used was a Riedel, Germany product. All other reagents and chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

pH-measurements were made on an Elico model LI-10, pH-meter. IR studies were performed on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. X-ray studies were made on a Philips X-ray unit using a Mo-K α target. Thermogravimetry was done on a modern TGA balance of the F. C. I. Ltd., India.

Synthesis of the ion-exchange material :

To a definite volume of aqueous sodium silicate solution (0.1 M) was added conc. HCl (5 ml per 100 ml of the solution) followed by a definite volume of thorium nitrate (0.1 M) solution. The pH of this mixture was adjusted to 9-10 by NaOH and the resultant slurry was allowed to stand overnight. It was then filtered, washed with demineralised water (DMW), and mixed with a fixed volume of the H_3PO_4 - HNO_3 mixture (1 M in terms of each acid). The gel thus obtained was filtered and washed thoroughly before drying at 45° in an air oven. The dried material was cracked in DMW to form small granules of uneven sizes. Fine particles were removed by decantation and the rest were placed in 1 M HNO_3 to convert them into the H^+ - form which were finally dried at 45° Table 1 summarizes the

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS OF SOME SAMPLES OF Th(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE AND THEIR Na^+ ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY

Sample	Mixing ratios of the solutions $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 : \text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O} :$ $(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 + \text{HNO}_3)$	Na^+ - ion exchange capacity (meq/dry g)
TPS-1	1 : 1 : 1	1.66
TPS-2	2 : 1 : 1	1.66
TPS-3	1 : 1 : 2	1.54
TPS-4	1 : 2 : 1	1.66

synthesis and Na^+ ion exchange capacity of the various samples prepared. Reproducibility was checked by preparing several samples by the same method and observing their ion-exchange capacity many times. All the studies were performed on the sample TPS-1.

Ageing effect: The gel was kept for different time intervals before filtering. After processing as above, their ion-exchange capacity was determined as usual. The results are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF AGING ON THE ION EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF Th(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE (TPS-1)

Ageing time (hr)	Na ⁺ - ion exchange capacity (meq/g)
24	1.66
48	1.68
72	1.74
120	1.78
240	1.82
360	1.91
480	1.92

Composition of the material: A weighed amount (500 mg) of the powdered exchanger was dissolved in conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml) by heating. After dilution to ~100 ml with water, thorium was precipitated¹⁰, filtered, ignited and weighed as ThO₂. Phosphorous was determined as phosphate by back titration with EDTA¹¹ and silica was determined as SiO₂¹². The results are summarized in Table 3 which are the mean of atleast five observations.

TABLE 3—COMPOSITION OF Th(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE

Sample	Millimoles of components per 500 mg of the exchanger			Mole ratio Th : P : Si
	Thorium	Phosphorous	Silicon	
TPS-1	1.39	1.78	1.56	1 : 1.28 : 1.12
TPS-2	1.38	1.44	2.12	1 : 1.04 : 1.53
TPS-3	1.42	1.56	1.84	1 : 1.09 : 1.29
TPS-4	1.64	1.36	1.68	1 : 0.82 : 1.02

Ion-exchange capacity (iec): This was determined as usual by the column process¹³. The values in meq/g (dry) for different metals are Li(I) (0.98), Na(I) (1.66), K(I) (1.68), NH₄(I) (0.82), Mg(II) (1.54), Ba(II) (0.96), Ca(II) (1.11). The Na⁺ iec of the irradiated samples (1 × 10⁸, 2 × 10⁸ and 3 × 10⁸ rads) were found to be 1.44, 1.34 and 1.21 meq/g, respectively.

Elution behaviour: The optimum concentration of NaNO₃ for the complete elution of hydrogen ions in a fixed volume (125 ml) from the exchanger was found to be 1 M. The elution curve was then drawn by taking this concentration of the eluant and is shown in Fig. 1.

Irradiation effect: Different samples of thorium(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS-1) were irradiated by γ -rays obtained from a ⁶⁰Co source under a dose rate of 0.4 M rads/hr, the total doses being 1 × 10⁸, 2 × 10⁸ and 3 × 10⁸ rads, respectively using FeSO₄ as the dosimeter. The ion-exchange behaviour of these irradiated samples was studied as mentioned above.

Fig. 1. Elution behaviour of Th(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS-1).

Thermal stability: Several samples were heated at different temperatures for 1 hr each and the iec was determined as above after cooling them to room temperature. It was observed that the material retains about 80% of its iec at 200° beyond which it loses it very sharply.

Chemical stability: 250 mg of the material was placed in 25 ml solution of an acid or a base and shaken intermittently for 24 hr. The solution was then analyzed for dissolved thorium¹⁴, phosphorous¹⁵ and silica¹⁶ contents using standard spectrophotometric methods. The results are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—SOLUBILITY OF THORIUM(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE (TPS-1) IN VARIOUS SOLVENT

Solution 25 ml	Amount dissolved in mg/250 mg of the exchanger		
	Th	P	Si
1 M HNO ₃	1.5	0.0	1.8
2 M HNO ₃	3.0	1.8	3.8
1 M HClO ₄	2.8	0.0	3.4
2 M HClO ₄	3.2	0.0	6.3
2 M HCl	3.5	1.4	6.3
1 M H ₂ SO ₄	6.3	3.0	6.8
1 M CH ₃ COOH	2.5	1.4	1.5
1 M KNO ₃	0.0	1.5	0.0
1 M NaNO ₃	1.3	0.0	0.0
1 M NH ₄ NO ₃	1.3	0.0	1.5
0.05 M NaOH	3.0	2.5	6.8
0.1 M NaOH	3.0	3.9	6.8
0.1 M KOH	2.8	3.3	2.5

pH-Titrations: 500 mg of the exchanger was taken in each of several 250 ml conical flasks followed by equimolar solutions (0.05 M) of alkali metal chlorides and their hydroxides in different volume ratios, the final volume being 50 ml. The pH values recorded after keeping the solutions overnight for equilibrium were plotted against the milliequivalents of OH⁻ added (Fig. 2). It shows a monofunctional

Fig. 2. pH-Titration curve for Th(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS-1).

behaviour similar to that of a strong acid cation exchanger.

These studies were performed on sample TPS-1 for different metal ions in various solvents in the following manner.

250 mg exchanger beads in H⁺ form were equilibrated with 25 ml of the selected solvent by shaking at room temperature for 4 hr. The exchanger beads were separated by decantation and the solution was analyzed volumetrically for the presence of metal ions, using EDTA as titrant¹⁷. The initial metal ion concentration was so adjusted that it may not exceed 3% of the total iec of the material. The K_a values, as summarized in Table 5, were then calculated by the formula

$$K_a = \frac{I-F}{F} \times \frac{V}{A} \text{ (ml/g)}$$

where I is the initial volume of EDTA used, F the final volume of EDTA used, V the total volume of the solution, and A the amount of exchanger in g.

Separations achieved : Based on the distribution behaviour, several binary separations were achieved on a column having 2 g of the exchanger in H⁺ form, taken in a glass tube having an i.d. ~0.6 cm. The flow rate was maintained at ~0.5 ml/min. Table 6 summarizes the results along with the limits of separation of Hg(II) from Zn(II), Cd(II) and Cu(II). The height equivalent to a theoretical plate (HETP) was also calculated¹⁸ to demonstrate the efficiency of the column, using the formula

$$HETP = \frac{Lb^2}{8V_{max}^2}$$

where L is the column height (7.5 cm), b the peak width (ml) at a height of 0.368 C_{max} and V_{max} the eluant volume (ml) at peak.

Results and Discussion

Thorium(IV) phosphosilicate thus turns out to be a selective cation exchanger for Hg(II). It can be used effectively for column chromatographic separation of Hg(II) from other metal ions, as Table 6 shows. Mercury has also been separated from some

synthetic alloys (amalgams) such as Zn(II)-Hg(II), Cd(II)-Hg(II), Cu(II)-Hg(II), Mn(II)-Hg(II) and Ni(II)-Hg(II), the upper limit of separation being 401.18 μg Hg(II) per 2 g of the column. Thus, the material appears to have a potential application in analytical field. The advantage of the method lies in its simplicity and versatility. The iec of the material increases on ageing the gel formed after mixing the component solutions (Table 2) which is obvious because of the equilibrium attained by the system with time. The material shows a monofunctional behaviour (Fig. 2) which may be due to similar pK_a values¹⁹ of the two acid groups present in it.

The thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 3) shows the first inflexion point at 160°, corresponding to a weight loss of ~20%, which may be due to the removal of external water molecules from the gel.

Fig. 3. Thermogram of Th(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS-1). ▯

After this temperature the loss rate is considerably slowed down probably because of the condensation process which continues upto ~400°, the total loss at that temperature being ~25%. The composition studies also indicate nearly the same amount of water content in the material thus confirming the TGA results. On the basis of chemical analysis, ir and TGA studies, the formula of this salt may be tentatively suggested as :

If we assume the weight due to the presence of the external water molecules in the gel as ~20% of the total weight, the number of such moles (n) per mole of the exchanger can be determined on the basis of the Alberti's equation²⁰

$$18n = \frac{X(M+18n)}{100}$$

where X is the percent water content and M+18n the molecular weight of the material. It gives the value of n as 6.3.

TABLE 5— K_d VALUES OF SOME METAL IONS ON THORIUM(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE (TPS-1)

Sl. No.	Metal Ion	DMW*	0.01 M HCl	0.1 M HCl	0.01 M HNO ₃	0.1 M HNO ₃	0.01 M HClO ₄	0.1 M HClO ₄	0.01 M CH ₃ COOH	0.1 M CH ₃ COOH
1.	Zn(II)	110	50	33	28	10	48	18	40	14
2.	Cd(II)	100	64	25	67	7	52	26	72	12
3.	Hg(II)	1900	1150	1150	1120	1120	1120	1120	1120	1120
4.	Mg(II)	110	86	48	64	18	92	38	92	18
5.	Ca(II)	78	64	26	36	14	55	12	46	16
6.	Sr(II)	160	102	86	78	42	110	84	94	66
7.	Ba(II)	860	586	410	778	542	568	398	586	420
8.	Mn(II)	80	28	0	16	13	42	8	32	12
9.	Fe(III)	200	61	0	73	0	0	0	0	0
10.	Co(II)	975	620	485	616	79	616	79	616	79
11.	Ni(II)	75	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0
12.	Cu(II)	45	15	8	17	1	28	22	16	0
13.	Pb(II)	925	441	130	598	138	496	128	778	285
14.	Al(III)	98	0	0	0	0	5	0	5	0

*Demineralised water.

TABLE 6—SALIENT FEATURES OF SOME SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON THORIUM(IV) PHOSPHOSILICATE (TPS-1) COLUMNS

Sl. No.	Separation achieved	Amount loaded (μ g)	Amount found (μ g)	% Error	Limit of loading in μ g on 1 g exchanger	Eluent used (ml)	HETP (cm)
1.	Zn(II)-Hg(II)	254.9 Zn	254.9 Zn	0	58-300	0.01 M HNO ₃ , (40)	1.35
		581.7 Hg	581.7 Hg	0	40-850	1 M HNO ₃ , (50)	—
2.	Cd(II)-Hg(II)	168.6 Cd	168.6 Cd	0	85-400	0.01 M HNO ₃ , (20)	1.84
		401.2 Hg	401.2 Hg	0	40-590	1 M HNO ₃ , (40)	—
3.	Cu(II)-Hg(II)	197.0 Cu	197.0 Cu	0	68-250	0.01 M HNO ₃ , (30)	2.4
		481.2 Hg	401.2 Hg	-4.8	40-590	1 M HNO ₃ , (40)	—
4.	Cu(II)-Pb(II)	133 Cu	132 Cu	-2	20-400	0.01 M HCl, (40)	7.4
		310 Pb	290 Pb	-6.4	150-550	0.1 M HCl, (30)	—
5.	Cu(II)-Co(II)	287 Cu	287 Cu	0	100-650	0.1 M HCl, (30)	6.34
		232 Co	219 Co	-5.6	65-480	1 M HCl, (30)	—
6.	Ni(II)-Co(II)	163 Ni	159 Ni	-2.45	60-400	0.1 M HNO ₃ , (40)	1.84
		118 Co	95 Co	-11	150-350	1 M HNO ₃ , (40)	—
7.	Mg(II)-Ba(II)	443 Mg	443 Mg	0	30-580	DMW, (40)	1.84
		297 Ba	297 Ba	-3.3	40-600	0.1 M HCl, (30)	—
8.	Ca(II)-Ba(II)	443 Ca	443 Ca	0	24-800	DMW, (60)	2.4
		524 Ba	524 Ba	0	40-800	0.1 M HCl, (20)	—

The ir spectrum of this material (Fig. 4) shows several peaks. The broad bands at 600 cm^{-1} is due to polymerization through metal-oxygen linkages and are expected to impart ion exchange properties. The sharp peaks at 750 and 1050 cm^{-1} are due to the presence of the silicate and phosphate groups²¹, respectively, while those at 1600 and 3200 cm^{-1} represent the "interstitial" and "external" water molecules. The ir spectra of the irradiated samples (Fig. 4) are essentially similar to that of the normal

Fig. 4. IR spectra of Th(IV) phosphosilicate (TPS-1).

sample, indicating that the material is generally unaffected by the γ -irradiation upto a total dose of 3×10^6 rads. The icc and elution behaviour are however slightly affected by this treatment as is indicated in Figs. 1 and 2. This study, therefore, clearly illustrates the advantage of using thorium(IV) phosphosilicate under the environment of strong radiations in which the organic resins²² start decomposing even much below the range studied here.

The distribution studies (Table 5) indicate that, in general, with the increase of the H^+ ion concentration, the K_d values decrease, which is an obvious phenomenon. However, the decrease is not linear with the pH , which may be due to the adsorption process, in addition to the pure ion exchange phenomenon taking place on the surface of an inorganic ion exchanger. A definite view in this regard cannot be taken at the moment because of the lack of a thorough study of the distribution behaviour on this material. Such studies are in progress. The most striking feature of the study, however, is the fact that the material is highly selective for Hg(II) in all the systems studied even at low pH .

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